

EVALUATION OF THE MANAGEMENT OF PULMONARY HYDATID CYST IN CHILDREN ACCORDING TO DIFFERENT SURGICAL TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

Author presents a study evaluating the effectiveness of surgical treatment in pulmonary hydatid cyst in children. The study group included 90 cases (81.82 %) patients with pulmonary hydatidosis and 20 (18.8) with hepatopulmonary cyst. 2 surgical techniques were used: padding with sealing of the residual cavity and the pneumostomy procedure. The results of the study allowed to conclude: The higher rate of postoperative complications compared to the uncomplicated forms of the disease, together with the presented evolutionary aspects, confirms the need to optimize the methods of surgical removal of residual postechinococcectomy cavities in cases of uncomplicated and complicated by rupture pulmonary hydatid cyst with the aim of reducing postoperative morbidity and duration of hospitalization, there being major risks of developing complications in cases of long persistence of residual cavities.

The cystotomy procedure with the removal of the parasitic larvocyst completed with the closure of the air bronchial communications completed with filling hemostatic collagen sponge, or sponge with gelatin and platelet concentrate, and the padding of the remaining cavity with the preservation of the adjacent lung parenchyma is an effective method of treating the pulmonary hydatid cyst in children, this surgical method having a lower incidence of postoperative morbidity compared to pneumostomy procedure.

In uncomplicated pulmonary hydatid cyst in children, the pericystic tissues have an increased potential of regeneration, which significantly influences the favorable evolution of the processes of repair and obliteration of remaining cavities in cases of dehiscence of padding sutures. In this context, we believe that in cases of dehiscence of padding sutures, children can be treated conservatively.

Keywords: Hydatid cyst, lung, treatment, surgery, children.

Introduction

Surgical treatment remains the curative option of choice in the treatment of hydatid cyst. The principles of surgical treatment in pulmonary hydatid cyst are: evacuation of the larvocyst with removal of the endocyst, avoidance of intraoperative contamination, as well as the management of the residual cavity with maximum preservation of the lung parenchyma, including the major sizes formations [1, 26]. Several surgical procedures are described in the specialized literature, which can be classified into conservative (cystostomy, enucleation of the intact cyst, removal of the cyst after needle aspiration or pericystectomy, with maximum preservation of the lung parenchyma) and radical (lung parenchyma resection with cystostomy and pericystectomy, wedge resection, segmentectomy and lobectomy [6, 12, 25].

The aim of this study was to retrospectively evaluate the results of surgical treatment in various forms of pulmonary hydatid cyst according to the surgical method of the postechinococcectomy residual cavities based on the results of the morphopathological examination.

Material and methods. From the total number of patients included in the study group, the majority were boys, both in the group of patients with pulmonary hydatid cyst - 66.67%, and in the group with coexisting hepatic forms - 65%, the maximum frequency being recorded at the age of 7 -14 years in both groups of patients.

Depending on the location, in the group of patients with isolated pulmonary hydatid cyst, the right lung

was more frequently affected - 52 (57.78%) cases, compared to the left - 21 (23.33%) cases, in 17 (18, 9%) cases the parasitic lesion involving both lungs. The lower lung lobes were more frequently involved, predominantly the lower lobe of the right lung (38.9%). Patients with single pulmonary hydatid cysts predominated - 63 (70%) cases, compared to those with multiple parasitic cyst formations - 27 (30%) cases. Giant lung cysts, with a diameter of more than 10 cm, were found in 32 (35.56%) cases, and in 19 (21.11%) cases, the pulmonary hydatid cysts complicated by rupture were detected.

Taking into account the pericystic changes, found at the imaging examination, similar to the groups of patients included in the morphopathological study, the patients undergoing surgical treatment were evaluated and divided into 3 subgroups: group 1 – with insignificantly expressed perifocal changes, group 2 – with significant pericystic inflammatory changes and group 3 – with pulmonary cysts complicated by rupture.

The patients of the study group benefited from routine laboratory tests (100% of cases) and imaging investigations that included: chest radiography, performed in 100% of cases, computer tomography, abdominal ultrasound examination and lung perfusion scintigraphy.

The statistical analysis of the obtained results was performed using the Evidence-Based Medicine Toolbox Program for analytical studies. The RR was calculated, the significance of the results was established based on the z-statistic test, 95% CI and the significance threshold, the result being statistically significant when the confidence interval does not include the

value 1 or the difference between the lower and upper limit is not large.

Results and discussions. In uncomplicated forms of pulmonary hydatid cyst, we gave preference to aspiration of hydatid fluid with a thick needle with intraoperative inactivation of the parasitic larvocyst with a scolicedal substance, later resorting to cystotomy (pneumostomy) and extraction of the larvocyst, taking into account the aparazitarian principles. As substances with scolicedal action were used: Alcohol 96⁰ (21 cases – 19.1%), betadine (32 cases – 29.1%), hypertonic solution 10% (5 cases – 4.5%), silver nitrate solution 1.5% (52 cases – 47.3%), without giving preference to one of them.

At the same time, the inner surface of the fibrous capsule was processed with argon plasma. After processing the remaining cavity with a scolicedal substance, in all cases we resorted to closing the bronchial openings, in 18 cases resorting to an additional protection of their sutures with a collagen hemostatic sponge or with gelatin sponge and platelet concentrate + thrombin + CaCl 10% (18 cases). In all cases, we used 3-0 Vicryl suture in the padding process of the remaining cavities. Regardless of the form of the disease, pericystic changes and dimensions, 50 ml of Aminocaproic acid solution was introduced into the pleural cavity and the aspiration drainage of the pleural cavity by Bulau being installed, which was removed when air leakage or exudate disappeared.

In the cases of using pneumostomy to solve the outstanding cavities, we resorted to resection of the fibrous capsule with preservation of the adjacent lung tissue, closure of air communications, drainage of the outstanding cavities and the pleural cavity.

Economical lung resections were performed in 4 cases of uncomplicated parasitic cyst formations, of small sizes (4-5 cm), peripherally located, which did not create any technical problems. Pulmonary lobectomy, enucleation and pericystectomy were not performed in any patient.

In the complicated forms with the rupture of the parasitic cyst, the cystotomy procedure was performed with the removal of hydatid larvocyst fragments, healing with substances with a scolicedal effect and drainage of the remaining cavity, including in cases of using the padding procedure. We also note that in the complicated forms of the disease, to protect and close the bronchial fistulas, we used collagen hemostatic sponge or sponge with gelatin and platelet concentrate.

In all 3 study groups, preference was given to the padding procedures of the residual cavities over the use of the pneumostomy procedure or lung resections. The analysis of the obtained results allowed us to find that in all 3 study groups no fatal cases were registered and there was no case of severe postoperative complication, which would require a surgical reintervention.

In the cases of uncomplicated hydatid cyst of small and medium sizes included in the 1st group of patients, no postoperative complications were recorded, the patients being discharged from the hospital 8-10 days postoperatively, 30-60 days postoperatively, insignificant residual post-echinococectomy signs were observed. In study group nr. 1, no recurrence cases have been recorded so far. All complications found in group 1 patients and described in tab. 2 were solved by conservative methods. Cases of pulmonary atelectasis, septic complications were not found. The duration of pleural drainage in cases of using the padding procedure without postoperative complications was 72 hours

We mention that in the cases of uncomplicated large-sized hydatid cyst (32 cases) or in the complicated forms, along with pulmonary ventilation disorders, confirmed by spirometry and changes in pulmonary perfusion in the pericystic segments, signs of hepatomegaly with diffuse parenchymatous liver changes were found, an important fact in the evaluation of patients in the postoperative period and the establishment of recovery treatment tactics.

All 19 cases of dehiscence of padding sutures found in group 1 were found in children with uncomplicated hydatid cyst of major and giant sizes, of which in 10 cases remaining cavities after the pneumostomy procedure were found. The complete obliteration of the residual cavities, initially radiologically detected in patients with echinococectomy and padding of the remaining cavity in which partial insufficiency of the padding sutures developed postoperatively (9 cases), was 62 ± 9 days. In this context, we demonstrate the case of patient P., 9 years old (fig. 1), who underwent the echinococectomy operation with padding of the remaining cavity by suturing in superimposed bursae with resorbable threads and final “back-and-forth” suturing plan by plan, on the 6th postoperative day, the partial insufficiency of the padding sutures, including the closing suture of the bronchial openings occurred, but without signs of worsening of the pulmonary perfusion in the remaining lung segments (fig. 1).

Later, the chest x-ray revealed the gradual obliteration of the remaining cavity until its complete disappearance with the re-expansion of the adjacent segments (fig. 2). The results found in the radiological examination are gratifying, the positive postoperative evolution being also confirmed by the lung scintigraphy, where the gradual improvement of the pulmonary perfusion indices in the affected lung with a slow regional redistribution in the contralateral lung was found. However, lung scintigraphy showed the maintaining of some local changes (even over 5 years after the operation). These findings are valid for all cases of uncomplicated pulmonary hydatid cyst of major and giant sizes included in study group 1.

Table 1.

The distribution of surgical procedures performed in the subgroups of patients with pulmonary hydatid cyst

The technical procedure used	Group I, n=58		Group II, n=33		Group III, n=19	
	Cases	%, 95%CI CI	Cases	%, 95% CI	Cases	%, 95% CI
Pulmonary echinococectomy + pneumostomy	10	17,24 7,5212- 26,9614	6	18,18 5,0209- 31,3391	7	36,84
Pulmonary echinococectomy + padding of the remaining cavity according to Delbet	12	20,69 10,2648- 31,1152	7	21,21 7,2622- 35,1578	2	10,53
Echinococectomy + padding of the remaining cavity by suturing in overlapped bursae with resorbable threads and final "back-and-forth" suturing plan by plan	12	20,69 10,2648- 31,1152	9	27,27 12,0751- 42,4649	3	15,79
Echinococectomy + suturing of the bronchial fistula + filling with hemostatic collagen material + padding of the remaining cavity by suturing in overlapped bursae with resorbable threads and final "back-and-forth" suturing plan by plan	10	17,24 7,5212- 26,9614	6	18,18 5,0209- 31,3391	2	10,53
Echinococectomy + suturing of the bronchial fistula + filling with hemostatic material with gelatin and platelet concentrate + padding of the remaining cavity by suturing in overlapped bursae with resorbable threads and final "back-and-forth" suturing plan by plan	10	17,24 7,5212- 26,9614	3	9,1 -0,7130- 18,9130	5	26,31
Marginal (atypical) economic lung resections	4	6,9 0,3771- 13,4229	2	6,06 -2,0807- 14,2007	0	

Fig. 1. Patient P., 9 years old. Chest X-ray in 2 projections performed preoperatively (A, B) – a voluminous oval-shaped formation located in the lower lobe of the left lung is found; C – preoperative lung scintigraphy (perfusion) – significant decrease in blood flow in the middle and lower segments of the left lung; D – liver scintigraphy – parenchymal changes

Fig. 2. Patient P., 9 years old. Chest X-ray in 2 projections performed at the time of hospital discharge (A), where the partial dehiscence of the padding sutures is found, and the dehiscence of the closure suture of the bronchus communicating with the remaining cavity is also confirmed at CT (B). C - postoperative pulmonary scintigraphy (perfusion) performed on the 12th postoperative day: the perfusion changes observed are similar to the preoperative result; D - X-ray of the chest taken 5 years after the operation: on the left parahilar, the deformation of the lung pattern (reticular type) is maintained, without any nodular or cavitary formations, the costo-diaphragmatic sinus is clear, a few supradiaphragmatic deposits are visualized. Conclusion: positive evolution, local pneumofibrosis in regression; E - Pulmonary scintigraphy (perfusion) in 2 projections performed 5 years after the surgery – on the background of an uneven distribution of the radiopharmaceutical substance in the left lung with a moderate diffuse decrease of blood flow, in the S10 projection of the left lung, an area of hypoperfusion of the substance is detected; in the right lung changes in blood flow are not detected.

The use of the pneumostomy procedure in subgroup 1 patients is determined by a relatively higher incidence of complications compared to the padding procedure, but acceptable results have been obtained both in cases of hydatid cyst of small and medium sizes, as well as in the cysts of major sizes. Clinically, the early postoperative period in the cases of using the pneumostomy procedure evolved comparatively more seriously with polypnea, cough, chest pain, early postoperative radiography presenting a remaining cavity and residual free air in all 10 cases, which usually reabsorbed

during the first 7-10 postoperative days. In the cases of using the pneumostomy procedure, a negative pressure was obtained in the pleural cavity within 3-5 days, the duration of pleural drainage was 12 ± 4 days because of the serous eliminations, the removal of the drainage from the remaining cavity being performed within 32 ± 7 days. Radiologically, true signs of size reduction of the residual cavity are observed after 30 days from the surgery, and its obliteration - approximately after 60 days, signs of persistence of the residual cavities being visualized also after 120 days from the surgery (fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Patient A., 9 years old. Chest X-ray (A), preoperative CT (B) - hydatid cyst of the left lung with compression of the mediastinal organs, diffuse hyperinflation of the upper lobe of the left lung, adjacent pneumofibrotic changes, thickening of the interlobular pleura; C - The intraoperative aspect of the residual cavity of impressive sizes after the removal of the hydatid larvocyst; the presence of an air communication (communicating bronchus) with the residual cavity is observed; D - Chest X-ray taken on the 75th postoperative day: a significant reduction of the residual cavity with perifocal infiltration and local thickening of the paracostal pleura is noted; E - Chest X-ray taken 120 days postoperatively: signs of persistence of a small residual cavity with resorption of perifocal infiltrative areas are visualized; F - Chest X-ray taken 1 year after surgery: disappearance of the residual cavity with the presence of residual pneumofibrotic signs and contralateral compensatory emphysema;

All 3 cases of persistent pneumothorax occurred after suture dehiscence of the large-caliber bronchial closure with opening into the residual cavity. There were 6 cases of prolonged air leaks, which were resolved conservatively by aspiration drainage. The postoperative evolution of uncomplicated cases of pulmonary hydatid cyst included in group 2 was similar to group 1. In the cases of using the pneumostomy procedure in group 2 patients, the duration of pleural drainage was 16 ± 4 days, and the removal of the drain from the remaining cavity was performed within 41 ± 6 days.

Despite the thorough closing of the air bronchial communications, in all 6 cases of pneumostomy procedure the persistence of the remaining cavity was found, in 4 cases prolonged air leaks were found, of which 2 cases with the development of compressive pneumothorax determined by the dehiscence of the sutures

closing the large caliber bronchial communications. In the cases of using the padding of the remaining cavity, the development of this complication was found in the cases of the Delbe procedure - 3 cases, in one case with the development of pneumothorax, in the padding of the remaining cavity by suturing in superimposed bursae with absorbable threads - 1 case and 1 case in the padding and filling with collagen material of the remaining cavity. All cases of prolonged air leaks and pneumothorax were solved conservatively. The case of atelectasis diagnosed after the pneumostomy procedure was solved with the help of bronchoscopy with complete re-expansion of the atelectazosed segment. There were no cases of pleuro-pulmonary or wound septic complications.

The case of compressive pneumothorax, which developed as a result of the dehiscence of the closing sutures of the large-caliber bronchial communications and the padding sutures in the case of using the padding procedure of the remaining cavity, once again confirmed the veracity of the morphopathological results found in operated patients included in group 2, who assumed a major risk of developing some postoperative complications, determined by the inflammatory-necrotic processes of the fibrous capsule. It should be noted that in group 2 a case of dehiscence of the padding sutures with the subsequent development of a compressive pneumothorax was found in a patient with a medium-sized hydatid cyst but with perifocal inflammation, the residual cavity being solved by using the padding procedure according to Delbet.

All 3 cases of compressive pneumothorax detected in group 2 patients developed after the Delbet procedure (1 case) and pneumostomy (2 cases) had a serious postoperative evolution, with the development of an inflammatory-destructive bronchopulmonary process, the slow expansion of the collapsed lung and a long re-

covery period. In this context, we emphasize that a partial re-expansion of the collapsed lung occurred only starting from the 8th day after this complication appeared, this period having a duration of about 32 days, subsequently being observed the period of gradual reabsorption of the pneumonic infiltration with regression of the exudative pleurisy and the gradual obliteration of the remaining cavity, acceptable results of the treatment being observed starting from the 8th month after the surgical intervention. In study group 3, no recurrence cases have been noticed up to this point.

In study group 3, where the majority of cases were large and giant parasitic cysts, complete obliteration of remaining cavities in patients with echinococectomy and pneumostomy occurred in 155 ± 32 days. In cases of hydatid cyst complicated by endobronchial eruption, the use of the padding procedure made it possible to obtain obliteration of the residual cavity within 94 ± 5 days. Even in giant forms, with significant inflammatory changes, positive results were obtained (fig. 4). In this group of patients, 2 cases of recurrent hydatid cyst were found.

Fig. 4. Patient P.A., 11 years old. Preoperative CT (A, B, C): pulmonary hydatid cyst with endobronchial eruption (floating membrane sign is visualized) located in the middle lobe of the right lung CT performed 62 days postoperatively (D, E, F) – obliteration of the remaining cavity with a perifocal infiltrative process is observed

he persistence of the residual cavity characteristic for the pneumostomy procedure in all cases of pulmonary hydatid cyst complicated by rupture with prolonged air leakage, and the dehiscence of the sutures closing the large-caliber bronchial communications

were the cause of developing the compressive pneumothorax in 3 cases compared to the padding procedure (1 case). This fact can be explained by necrotic degeneration changes of the pericystic layer that we found in the morphopathological study and presented in the specialized literature [10].

Table 2.

Comparative analysis of the incidence of postoperative complications in the 3 study subgroups according to the procedure used for solving the remaining cavity

Type of complications	Group 1 58 cases		Group 2 33 cases		Group 3 19 cases	
	<i>Pns.</i> 10 cases	<i>Padd.</i> 48 cases	<i>Pns.</i> 6 cases	<i>Padd.</i> 27 cases	<i>Pns.</i> 7 cases	<i>Padd.</i> 12 cases
Postoperative pneumothorax	2 (20 %)	-	2 (30%)	1 (3,7%)	3 (42,8%)	1 (8,3%)
Cutaneous emphysema	-	-	-	-	1 (14,3%)	-
Persistence of residual cavities	10 (100%)	9 (18,75%)	6 (100%)	7 (25,9%)	7 (100 %)	4 (33,3%)
Prolonged air leak (>7 days)	4 (40%)	1 (2,08%)	4 (60%)	4 (14,8%)	7 (100%)	-
Atelectasis	-	-	-	1 (3,7)	1 (14,3%)	-
Septic complications	-	-	-	-	1 (14,3%)	-

*Note: Pns. - the remaining cavity solved by the pneumostomy procedure;
Padd. - the remaining cavity solved by the padding procedure;

The evaluation of the risk of development the postoperative complications found out that in the first subgroup the padding procedure is safer with a lower risk of developing dehiscence of the padding sutures and the persistence of residual cavities, in the evaluation of the risk of developing complications such as postoperative pneumothorax and prolonged air leaks were not being found statistically true values. In subgroup 2, in cases of pneumostomy procedure was a significantly higher risk of developing dehiscence of padding sutures with the persistence of residual cavities, but also of prolonged air leaks. In subgroup 3, the same law is maintained, there is a greater risk of developing the dehiscence of the padding sutures with the persistence of the remaining cavity, not being found any statistically veridical comparative values in the evaluation of the risk of developing other severe postoperative complications.

The relative risk for the persistence of residual cavities was found to be the highest in subgroup 1 RR=5.3 (95% CI: 2.9596 to 9.6108) and the lowest in subgroup 3 RR=3.0 (95% CI: 1.3478 to 6.6777).

The comparison of the results from the three subgroups where the remaining cavity was solved by pneumostomy or padding, according to the non-parametric Pearson criterion, proved that there is no statistically significant difference between the complications observed in the study subgroups.

The treatment of the hydatid cyst became a topic of discussion starting in 1804 when Laenec found that these parasitic formations represent a phase of the life cycle of a tapeworm, subsequently several surgical procedures and chemotherapeutic treatment schemes were proposed [14, 21]. Despite the progresses made in the medical treatment of hydatid cyst in children, the optimal therapeutic option is not clearly defined [22, 28], the treatment of choice remains surgery, which can be performed safely, with low morbidity and minimal mortality rates [15]. Lateroposterior thoracotomy technique with muscle preservation, originally proposed by

Noirclerc et al. in 1973 and later described by Bethencourt and Holmes (1987) [3], was adapted and used in thoracic surgery in neonates and children of various ages with fairly good results [4, 17], including pulmonary hydatid cyst surgery [23]. The thoracotomy with muscle preservation procedure according to Jawad A.J. (1997) provide an excellent exposure in the management of neonatal and pediatric thoracic surgical pathologies, without intraoperative complications, with a comparatively good postoperative cosmetic effect. And if the removal of the parasitic larvocyst represents a unanimously accepted opinion to resort to echinococectomy, then in the management of the residual cavity there are several controversial opinions [14].

In hydatid cyst surgery, the effective resolution of residual cavities is of a major importance, especially in complicated forms. The non-padding procedure, applied in removal of residual cavities after echinococectomy, is presented by several authors as an alternative, since their padding does not shorten hospitalization time and the duration of air removal through the thoracic tube, nor does it prevent complications such as empyema, persistence of fistulas and air leaks, recurrence [11, 12, 27]. Approaching and suturing the edges of the residual cavity is not necessary, the lung parenchyma removes the space, and the surface of the lung at the site of the residual cavity is covered by the pleura. The non-padding procedure for the removal of residual postechinococectomy cavities is also supported in the case of children [7].

The technical procedure of creating a direct communication between the residual cavity and the pleural space, with the liquidation of bronchial fistulas, and external drainage after the removal of the hydatid metacestode, was proposed by Yacoubian H.D. and Dajani T. (1963), being considered applicable both in intact forms of pulmonary hydatid cyst and in complicated ones [29]. The method aims to maintain functionally uncompromised the pericystic lung tissue, the efficiency and safety of this strategy being described by

several authors [18]. This procedure, called the "pneumonostomy" technique, was also used in the treatment of lung abscesses [20].

Several authors support the idea that the padding of the residual cavities after echinococectomy is not an essential procedure in the surgical treatment of the pulmonary hydatid cyst, being motivated by the ability of the lung to expand with the disappearance of the cavities after a short period of time after the surgery [12]. At the same time, some authors support the advantage of surgical interventions with the preservation of the lung parenchyma and padding of the residual cavity [2], the usefulness of this technical procedure being also supported by us, including in complicated forms of the disease [5, 9]. This technique allows avoiding the development of bronchopleural fistulas, the long persistence of air leaks, the formation of purulent collections in the residual cavity and in the pleural cavity, etc. [14].

The decision for lobectomy, supported by some authors in certain situations [30], must be taken carefully even in cases of infected hydatid cysts, giant or multiple cysts involving the same lobe [16, 19], instead, the procedure with the preservation of the lung parenchyma being preferred [24], especially in children and in endemic areas, where the risk of recurrence is a real concern [8, 13].

Conclusions:

1. The cystotomy procedure with the removal of the parasitic larvocyst completed with the closure of the air bronchial communications completed with filling hemostatic collagen sponge, or sponge with gelatin and platelet concentrate, and the padding of the remaining cavity with the preservation of the adjacent lung parenchyma is an effective method of treating the pulmonary hydatid cyst in children, this surgical method having a lower incidence of postoperative morbidity compared to pneumostomy procedure.

2. In uncomplicated pulmonary hydatid cyst in children, the pericystic tissues have an increased potential of regeneration, which significantly influences the favorable evolution of the processes of repair and obliteration of remaining cavities in cases of dehiscence of padding sutures. In this context, we believe that in cases of dehiscence of padding sutures, children can be treated conservatively.

3. The higher rate of postoperative complications compared to the uncomplicated forms of the disease, together with the presented evolutionary aspects, confirms the need to optimize the methods of surgical removal of residual postechinococectomy cavities in cases of uncomplicated and complicated by rupture pulmonary hydatid cyst with the aim of reducing postoperative morbidity and duration of hospitalization, there being major risks of developing complications in cases of long persistence of residual cavities.

References

1. Ahmad M., Khan S.A., Shah S.Z. et al. Effect of size on the surgical management of pulmonary hydatid cyst. *J. Ayub Me. Coll. Abbottabad*. 2014. 26(1):42-5.
2. Aldahmashi M., Alassal M., Kasb I., Elrakhawy H. Conservative surgical management for

pulmonary hydatid cyst: analysis and outcome of 148 cases. *HPC Canadian Resp. J.* 2016. Art. ID 8473070. 6 p. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2016/8473070>.

3. Ashour M. Modified muscle sparing posterolateral thoracotomy. *Thorax*. 1990. 45:935-8.

4. Askarpour S., Peyvaste M., Ashrafi A., Dehdashtian M., Malekian A., Aramesh M.R. Muscle-sparing versus standard posterolateral thoracotomy in neonates with esophageal atresia. *Arq. Bras. Cir. Dig.* 2018. 31(2):e1365. DOI: /10.1590/0102-672020180001e1365.

5. Babuci S., Petrovici V., Dogotari N., Malanco S., Pasicovschi T. Methods of intra-operative inactivation and surgical resolution of residual cavities in pulmonary hydatid cyst in children. *Mold. J. Pediatr. Surg.* 2017. 1:14-22.

6. Balci A.E., Eren N., Eren S., Ulku R. Ruptured hydatid cysts of the lung in children: clinical review and results of surgery. *Ann. Thorac. Surg.* 2002. 74:889-92.

7. Celik M., Şenol C., Keles M. et al. Surgical treatment of pulmonary hydatid disease in children: report of 122 cases. *J. pediatr. Surg.* 2000. 35:1710-3.

8. Dakak M., Caylak H., Kavakli K. et al. Parenchyma-saving surgical treatment of giant pulmonary hydatid cysts. *Thorac. Cardiovasc. Surg.* 2009. 57(3):165-8.

9. Dogotari N. Clinical-evolutionary and therapeutic features in complicated pulmonary hydatid cyst. *J. Pediatr.* 2016. XIX (Supl. 1):115.

10. Dogotari N., Gudumac E., Tica C., Eremia V., Ionescu C., Babuci S. Clinical and morphological considerations in pulmonary hydatid cyst complicated by endobronchial rupture in children. *ARS Medica Tomitana*. 2017. 2(23):72-8.

11. Erdogan A., Ayten A., Demircan A. Methods of surgical therapy in pulmonary hydatid disease: is capitonnage advantageous? *Aust. NZ J Surg.* 2005. 75:992-6.

12. Eren M.N., Balci A.E., Eren E. Non-capitonnage method for surgical treatment of lung hydatid cysts. *Asian Cardiovasc. Thorac. Ann.* 2005. 13(1):20-3.

13. Eyboglu T.S., Gursoy T.R., Aslan A.T., Pekcan S., Budkoglu I.I. Ten-year follow-up of children with hydatid cysts. *Turk. Pediatr. Ars.* 2019. 54(3):173-8.

14. Gudumac E., Babuci S., Dogotari N. Historical considerations and contemporary issues in pulmonary hydatid cyst treatment. *Arta Medica*. 2016. 1(58):15-9.

15. Haberal M.A., Akar E., Dikis O.S., Kaya M. Surgical treatment of childhood pulmonary hydatidosis: an analysis of 25 cases. *Tanaffos*. 2018. 17(4):280-4.

16. Hasdiraz L., Oguzkaya F., Bilgin M. Is lobectomy necessary in the treatment of pulmonary hydatid cysts? *ANZ J. Surg.* 2006. 76:488-90.

17. Jawad A.J. Experience with modified posterolateral muscle-sparing thoracotomy in neonates, infants, and children. *Pediatr. Surg. Int.* 1997. 12:337-9.

18. Jehangir S., Kurian J.J., Jacob T.J. et al. Pneumonostomy in the surgical management of hydatid cyst of the lung. *Eur. J. Pediatr. Surg.* 2017. 27(2):171-6.

19. Kilic D., Findikcioglu A., Bilen A., Koc Z. Management of complicated hydatid cyst of the thorax. 2007. 77(9):752-7.
20. Lacey S.R., Kosloske A.M. Pneumonostomy in the management of pediatric lung abscess. J. Pediatr. Surg. 1983. 18(5):625-7.
21. Lupia T., Corcione S., Guerrero F., Costardi L., Ruffini E. Pulmonary echinococcosis or lung hydatidosis: a narrative review. Surg. Inf. 2020. 21(10):1-11. DOI: 10.1089/sur.2020.197.
22. Moroni S., Moscatelli G., Bournissen F.G., González N., Ballering G., et al. Abdominal cystic echinococcosis treated with albendazole. A pediatric cohort study. PLoS ONE. 2016. 11 (9): e0160472. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0160472.
23. Önal Ö., Demir Ö.F. Is bilateral staged muscle-sparing thoracotomy performed within 1 week for lung hydatid cysts safe for pediatric patients? Turk. Thorac. J. 2018. 19:84-8.
24. Oncel M., Sadi S.G., Tezcan B. et al. Parenchyma-preserving and minimally invasive thoracotomy technique in giant pulmonary hydatid cysts. Turk. Gogus Kalp Dama. 2015. 23(1):88-91.
25. Sadrizadeh A., Haghi S.Z., Masuom S.H.F. et al. Evaluation of the effect of pulmonary hydatid cyst location on the surgical technique approaches. Lung India. 2014. 31(4):361-5.
26. Sharifi-Mood B., Fazaeli A., Izadi Sh., Mokhtari S. Fifteen years experience with pulmonary hydatidosis in Zahedan, Iran. Iranian J. Parasitol. 2007. 2(4):7-11.
27. Turna A., Yilmaz M.A., Hacıbrahimoglu G. et al. Surgical treatment of pulmonary hydatid cysts: is capitonnage necessary? Ann. Thorac. Surg. 2002. 74:191-5.
28. Velasco-Tirado V., Alonso-Sardón M., Lopez-Bernus A. et al. Medical treatment of cystic echinococcosis: systematic review and meta-analysis. BMC Infect. Dis. 2018. 18:306. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-018-3201-y>.
29. Yacoubian H.D., Dajani T. Preliminary report on a new method of surgical management of hydatid cysts of the lung. Ann. Surg. 1963. 157(4):618-24.
30. Yekeler E., Karaarslan K., Yazicioglu A. et al. Lobectomy for pulmonary hydatid cyst. Turk. J. Med. Sci. 2013. 43:1024-9.

HEALTHCARE PRACTICE STANDARDS FOR PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM ACUTE MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

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ABSTRACT

The ever increasing development of our society has facilitated significant progress in nursing profession. Healthcare practice for patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction requires that professional medical nurses be constantly focused on various aspects of patients' condition. The major impact factors that define the specifics of the nursing care practice for these patients have proved to be providing of state-of-the-art effective care services to enable the patients' constant observation, assessment of the patients' special needs and healthcare planning based on the coronary syndrome progression. Delivery of high standards in healthcare practice in patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction is seen impracticable unless new methodology and approaches are introduced as to implementation of the nursing process concept and elaboration of a nursing care plan based on the individual patient's needs.

Keywords: healthcare, acute myocardial infarction, patients.

INTRODUCTION

Healthcare services have proved of significant importance for the entire process of patients' therapy. The healthcare standards tend to contribute to a considerable extent to a stable economy and a sustainable development of medical institutions. The practice standards serve as the fundamental method of assessment of the healthcare services. Also, these may be instrumental to comparability of the clinical outcomes and unified criteria and approaches to prevent further complications. The correct standard apprehension tends to ensure ever higher quality healthcare standards for the benefit of better efficiency, respectively. This may require an analysis of the needs of patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction, introduction of entirely new approach to services provided by healthcare professionals

in state-of-the-art clinics, lifetime enhancement of qualifications to full satisfaction of the needs of healthcare industry.

For the purposes of improvement of the healthcare practice standards in delivery of services to patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction, the medical nurse education assigns to medical nurses a new role to play and assumption of duties and responsibilities demanding specific knowledge to be acquired throughout continuing training and certifications. Every nurse in the present days must be the face which with his/her knowledge and competency shall address the ever increasing healthcare needs of population.

OBJECT

This research is aimed at analyzing the nurses' opinions with respect to the healthcare issues, services